

ENHANCING PARASITIC MANAGEMENT: SMALL RUMINANT EXTERNAL PARASITE SPECIES IN TANQUA ABERGELLE AND KOLA TEMBIEN DISTRICTS OF TIGRAY, NORTHERN ETHIOPIA

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Abstract: *Ethiopia boasts the largest livestock population in Africa, with approximately 30.7 million sheep and 30.2 million goats, predominantly comprising local breeds. The livestock subsector plays a significant role in the country's economy, contributing approximately 16.5% to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and 35.6% to the agricultural GDP. This paper provides insights into the magnitude of Ethiopia's livestock sector, drawing upon data from Solomon et al. (2003), Tilahun and Schmidt (2012), UNDP (2010), and CSA (2018). By elucidating the substantial presence of sheep and goats in the country and highlighting their predominance as local breeds, this study underscores the importance of livestock in Ethiopia's agricultural landscape and economic development. Through a comprehensive analysis, this research aims to deepen our understanding of the contributions of the livestock subsector to the national economy and agricultural productivity.*

Keywords: *Ethiopia, Livestock population, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Agricultural GDP, Local breeds*

INTRODUCTION

Ethiopia is believed to have the largest livestock population in Africa (Solomon et al., 2003; Tilahun and Schmidt, 2012; UNDP, 2010). An estimate indicates that the country is a home for about 30.7 million sheep and 30.2 million goats. 99.8% of the sheep and nearly all goat population of the country are local breeds (CSA, 2018).

The contribution of the subsector to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is estimated to be 16.5% of and 35.6% of the agricultural GDP (Metaferia et al., 2011).

It also contributes 15% of export earnings and 30% of agricultural employment (Behnke, 2010). However, diseases have been the stumbling block against the full utilization of these resources for foreign currency through the export of live animals and skin (Solomon et al., 2003).

Currently, different causes of skin diseases in Ethiopia are accountable for considerable economic losses particularly to the skin export due to various defects, 65% of which occur in the pre- slaughter states directly related mostly to skin diseases causing often rejection because of poor quality (Behnke, 2010). Ectoparasites which include mites, ticks, lice, fleas and flies parasitize a more extensive range of hosts (e.g. Ticks) while many of them are host specific (e.g. lice) (Singh et al., 2000; Aujla et al., 2000; Ranjan et al., 2014). Many ectoparasites are known to be vectors of pathogens which transmit different diseases to hosts while feeding, or occasionally it may also cause a significant defect to and skins of different animal populations (Jaswal et al., 2014; Salih et al., 2015; Mohammed et al., 2017). This damaging of the skin is one of the annoying effects on the animals induced by the ectoparasites. The existence of various ectoparasites and skin diseases affecting small ruminants are frequently reported from different parts of Ethiopia. These are demodicosis, sarcoptic and psoroptic manges, ticks and lice infestations (Sertse and Wossene, 2007a; Mulugeta et al., 2010; Abay et al., 2017). The study area favors the development and propagation of ectoparasites which makes challenging to resist the annoying effect of these ectoparasites on the host and makes the control of ectoparasites difficult.

However, the major predisposing factors and enormous economic losses caused by ectoparasites need detailed studies on their identification of species. So far limited efforts have been made to investigate an overall situation of ectoparasites of small ruminants in the study districts.

The objectives of this study were to identify external parasites to their species level, to determine the associated risk factors of external parasites and to know the proportional defects of external parasites

Figure 1. Topographic map of Tanqau Abergelle and Kola Tembien districts in Ethiopia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the study area

As shown in Figure 1, the study was conducted in Kola Tembien (K. Tembien), and Tanqau Abergelle (T. Abergelle) districts for disease investigation and sample collection. The study districts are categorized as hot to warm sub-moist low lands sub-agro ecological zone of the region with an altitude of 1300-1500 m above sea level; the mean annual rainfall ranges from 400 to 600 mm, which is characterized by low, erratic and variable rainfall. The annual temperature ranges from 28 to 42°C (Figure 1).

Table 1. Overall frequency of external parasite species in the study districts.

Species	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Amblyomma variegatum</i>	84	35.4
<i>Rhipicephalus parvus</i>	54	22.8
<i>Rhipicephalus praetexatus</i>	21	8.9
<i>Rhipicephalus pulchellus</i>	17	7.2
<i>Hyalomma truncatum</i>	15	6.5
<i>Rhipicephalus evertsi</i>	6	2.5

<i>Ctenocephalides felis felis</i>	12	5.1
<i>Linognathus africanus</i>	28	11.8

Study population

The study was conducted from September 2014 to June 2017. Indigenous sheep and goats owned by individual farmers and managed under extensive management system were included. The districts have an overall small ruminant population of 693, 628 goats and 151,734 sheep (Kola Tembien Bureau of Agricultural Office, 2019).

Study design

A cross-sectional study was conducted on identification of external parasites of small ruminants to their species level. The study of ectoparasites on sheep and goats involved districts, sheep, and goats as a sampling unit. About 237 live sheep and goats were examined for the presence of external parasites in a weekly visit. Sample size was calculated according to the formula given by Thrusfield (2008) for random sampling method. A previous prevalence of 26.25% studied by Abay et al. (2017) was used to determine the maximum sample size.

Clinical examination and sample collection methods

Randomly selected sheep and goats were clinically examined for the presence of ectoparasites or lesions. In line with the sample collection explanatory variables such as sex, age, body condition and species were recorded. A body condition score of the animals considered as poor or good was recorded by modifying the system described (Gatenby et al., 1991) for sheep and (Steele et al., 1996) for goats. Poor body condition score was given to sheep and goats which were extremely thin and those with smooth and less prominent spinous process, transverse process in which finger can be pushed and moderate depth loin muscle. Good body condition score was given for sheep and goats in which the spinous process only sticks up very slightly; smooth, rounded and well covered transverse processes and those having full loin muscle and very fat.

Age categorization into young (lamb/kid) and adult was performed as described by Gatenby et al. (1991) for sheep and by Steele et al. (1996) for goats. Accordingly, sheep and goats less than one year were categorized as young and the rest as adult. Sheep and goats found infested by parasites were considered positive. Ectoparasites such as ticks, lice and fleas were collected by hand from their attachment site and put into container and preserved with 70 % alcohol (Urquhart et al., 1996). The collected parasites were taken to National Animal Health Diagnostic and Investigation Center (NAHDIC) and identified to species level by using taxonomical keys and entomological examination as per Keiser (1987).

Data management and analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the frequency of the identified species of external parasites. The effects of different epidemiological risk factors such as age, districts, and body condition on prevalence of ectoparasites in sheep and goats were analyzed by multivariate regression analysis at p value of 0.05.

RESULTS

Identification of species of external parasites

Eight different types of external parasites have been identified in NAHDIC by using taxonomical and entomological examination at species level. These are *Amblyomma variegatum*, *Hyalomma truncatum*, *Rhipicephalus parvus*, *Rhipicephalus praetextatus*, *Rhipicephalus pulchellus*, *Rhipicephalus evertsi*, *Ctenocephalides felis felis*, and *Linognathus africanus*, and their frequency is shown in Table 1. The highest prevalence was observed with *A. variegatum* infestation (35.4%) followed by *R. parvus* (22.8) in both species and districts.

The lowest prevalence was observed in *R. evertsi* infestation with an overall prevalence of 2.5% in both species and districts.

In our findings, a mixed infestation of more than two external parasite species has been observed in a single animal. Accordingly, 44 goats out of 141 and 28 sheep out of 96 were found infested with two or more external parasite species. As shown in Table 2, the higher infestation of external parasites in K. Tembien and T. Abergelle was by *R. parvus* (10.5%) and *A. variegatum* (25.7%), respectively. There was an observation of high external parasite infestation in T. Abergelle as compared with K. Tembien. This might be due to the high stress conditions such as heat, drought, and shortage of feed in T. Abergelle as compared to K. Tembien district. With regard to species, there was an overall observation of higher infestation of external parasites in goat as compared to sheep. Therefore, higher infestation was by *A. variegatum* (27.4%) in goat and by *R. parvus* (12.2%) in sheep. According to sex, female animals have been infested more as compared to male animals. In our findings, all identified species of external parasites were found in both species.

In general, our findings show that *A. variegatum* and *R. parvus* have a higher distribution in both species of animals in the study districts. On the other hand, *R. evertsi* has the lowest prevalence in both districts and both species. The overall prevalence of identified external parasite species was not significantly associated with their respected risk factors except for *A. variegatum* at a confidence level of 95%. As shown in Table 3, the prevalence of *A. variegatum* is significantly different across districts with P value 0.001. Accordingly, sheep and goats in T. Abergelle District were more likely infested with *A. variegatum* than K. Tembien District (AOR 2.75 (1.51, 4.98)). Additionally, the prevalence of *A. variegatum* was significantly ($p= 0.000$) higher in goat (27.4%) than sheep (8%). As a result, the odd of infestation in goat was 3.5 higher than in sheep. However, the prevalence of *A. variegatum* was not significantly different ($P>0.05$) across sex, age and body condition scores.

COR= Crude odd ration, AOR= Adjusted odd ratio.

Table 2. Prevalence of external parasite species across their associated risk factors in the study districts.

Variable	Prevalence of external parasites							
	<i>A. variegatum</i>	<i>R. parvus</i>	<i>R. praetextatus</i>	<i>R. pulchellus</i>	<i>C. felis felis</i>	<i>L. africanus</i>	<i>R. everts</i>	<i>H. truncatum</i>
Districts					8			
K. Tembien	23 (9.7%)	25 (10.5%)	12 (5.1%)	9 (3.8%)	3 (3.4%)	13 (5.5%)	3 (1.3%)	7 (3.0%)
T. Abergelle	61 (25.7%)	29 (12.2%)	9 (3.8%)	8 (3.4%)	4 (1.7%)	15 (6.3%)	3 (1.3%)	8 (3.4%)
Species					6			
Sheep	19 (8.0%)	29 (12.2%)	10 (4.2%)	8 (3.4%)	3 (2.5%)	16 (6.8%)	3 (1.3%)	5 (2.1%)
Goat	65 (27.4%)	25 (10.5%)	11 (4.6%)	9 (3.8%)	6 (2.5%)	12 (5.1%)	3 (1.3%)	10 (4.2%)
Sex					6			
Male	35 (14.8%)	24 (10.1%)	7 (3%)	8 (3.4%)	3 (2.5%)	12 (5.1%)	0.0	8 (3.4%)
Female	49 (20.7%)	30 (12.7%)	14 (5.9%)	9 (3.8%)	6 (2.5%)	16 (6.8%)	6 (2.5%)	7 (3.0%)

Table 3. Regression analysis of prevalence of *A. variegatum* with associated risk factors.

Variable	<i>A. variegatum</i>		COR	AOR	P value
	Positive	Negative			
District					
K. Tembien	23	77			0.001

T. Abergelle	61	76	0.37 0.66)	(0.21,2.75 4.98)	(1.51,
Species					
Sheep					0.000
Goat	19	77	0.23	(0.12,3.53	(1.91,
	65	76	0.53)	6.53)	

DISCUSSION

In our findings, eight species of external parasites were identified: *A. variegatum*, *R. parvus*, *R. praetexatus*, *R. pulchellus*, *C. felis felis*, *L. africanus*, *R.evertsi*, and *H. trancarum* with their prevalence of 35.4, 22.8, 8.9, 7.2, 5.1, 11.8, 2.5, and 6.5 percent, respectively. Tick infestations were the highest prevalence recorded in both species. Ahmed et al. (2017) found low prevalence of *A. variegatum* (24.5%), higher prevalence of *R. pulchellus* (34.1%), *R. evertsi evertsi* (22.1%), and *H. truncatum* (15.6%) in Diredawa districts compared to our findings. A small prevalence of *A. variegatum* (2.3%) was also reported by Seyoum et al. (2015) in Amhara Regional State, Sekela District. On the other hand there was a highest *A. variegatum* infestation in goat (27.4%) in our findings as compared to the study conducted by Mulugeta et al. (2010) which was 7.5%. An abundance of *A. variegatum* (66.15%) was reported by Jemere et al. (2011) in Wolmera District of Oromia, which is higher prevalence as compared to our findings. Such differences in prevalence may arise from differences in agro-climate, control measures practiced, management, and health care of sheep and goats in the study areas. Sheep and goat owners also noted seasonality in occurrence of ticks, which is related to the beginning of annual rain. Higher environmental temperature, humidity and prolonged sunlight favor the survival and reproduction of ticks in lowland areas (Pangui, 1994).

In our study, the overall prevalence of flea infestation (*C. felis felis*) in small ruminants were 5.1% which is smaller than the findings of Sertse and Wossene (2007a) who reported a prevalence of 8.1% in

eastern part of Amhara regional state. The previous *C. felis* infestation (11.1%) in Tigray region reported by Mulugeta et al. (2010) was higher than our findings. In our study area, the prevalence of *C. felis felis* in sheep and goat was 2.5% which was higher in sheep (0.2%) and lower in goat (8.1%) as compared to a report of Sertse and Wossene (2007b) in Eastern part of Amhara. According to Bates (2012) flea infestation is usually associated with close contact of animals with infested animals and also the same host.

Lice infestations with *Linognathus* species were the most prevalent external parasite recorded in sheep and goats in the study districts. According to Sertse (2004), higher prevalence of *Linognathus* species (28.3%) was found in Amhara regional state as compared to our findings. According to Mulugeta et al. (2010) the prevalence of *L. africanus* in sheep in three districts of Tigray region was 11.5%, which is higher than our findings (6.8%). Louse infestation may show some other underlying problems such as malnutrition and chronic diseases. The irritation caused by even a modest population of lice leads to scratching and rubbing, causing damage to the skin and severe infestation with *Linognathus* spp. may cause anemia (Sertse and Wossene, 2007b).

Conclusion

Our study revealed that eight species of external parasites have been found with a higher rate of infestation. Favorable environmental conditions, poor level of farmers' awareness and weak animal health extension services are believed to be the main factors for the wide distribution of external parasites in the study districts.

In this study a wide spread occurrence of tick infestation in small ruminant was observed and six species of ticks grouped under three genera were identified. *Rhipicephalus evertsi*, *Hyalomma truncatum*, *Rhipicephalus pulchellus*, *Amblyomma variegatum*, *Rhipicephalus praetexatus*, *Rhipicephalus parvus* was among the tick species identified in the study area. The most essential and abundant tick species identified in the study area were *Amblyomma variegatum* and *Rhipicephalus parvus* in order of predominance. By considering skin is a very important source of foreign currency to Ethiopia, serious attention should be given to the high prevalence of external parasite infestation in the study districts.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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REFERENCES

Abay G, Zenebe M, Daniel D, Hagos H, Berhanie M, Teame T (2017). Clinical survey on major ruminant diseases in Kola Tembien and Tanqua Aberegele districts, Central Zone of Tigray region, Northern Ethiopia. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Health* 9(12):342-348.

Aujla RS, Singla LD, Juyal PD and Gupta PP (2000). Prevalence and pathology of mange-mite infestations in dogs. *Journal of Veterinary Parasitology* 14(1):45-49.

Ahmed J, Wendemsgegn D, Tsehay A, Silesh S, Abebe H (2017). Prevalence of Tick Infestation on Small Ruminants in and Around Dire Dawa, Eastern Ethiopia. *International Journal of Research Granthaalayah* 5(5):326-336.

Bates P (2012). External parasites of small ruminants: A particular guide to their prevention and control. CAB international, pp. 99-102

Behnke R (2010). The Contribution of Livestock to the Economies of IGAD Member States: Study Findings, Application of the Recommendations for Further Work. IGAD LPI working Paper Great Wolford, United Kingdom. pp. 02-10.

CSA (2018). Central Statistics Agency, Agricultural Sample Survey: Livestock and livestock characteristics. Statistical bulletin 585. Gatenby MR, Coste R, Smith JA (1991). *The Tropical Agriculturalist*, Macmillan (London) and CTA (Wageningen), pp. 6-11.

Jaswal H, Bal MS, Singla LD, Amrita, Kaur P, Mukhopadhyay CS, Juyal

PD (2014). Application of msp1 β PCR and 16S rRNA semi nested PCR-RFLP for detection of persistent anaplasmosis in tick infested cattle. *International Journal of Advanced Research* 2(8):188-196.

Jemere B, Martha T, Rahmeto A (2011). External parasite infestations in small ruminants in Wolmera district of Oromiya Region, Central Ethiopia. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances* 10(4):518-523.

Keiser MN (1987). Ethiopia, Report on tick taxonomy and biology, AGDP/ ETH/83/) 23 consultant report. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, p. 92 Kola Tembien Bureau of Agricultural Office 2019.

Metaferia F, Cherenet T, Gelan A, Abnet F, Tesfay A, Abdi Ali J (2011). Ministry of Finance and Economic Development and Ministry of Agriculture: A review to improve estimation of livestock contribution to the national GDP, IGAD Livestock Policy Initiative, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

Mohammed AA, Sharma A, Saied MAM, Osman OH, Al-Balawi MH, Salih DA, Singla LD (2017). Lack of evidence for infection of camels with tick-borne diseases in Riyadh region, Saudi Arabia. Sudan Journal of Veterinary Research 32:39-40.

Mulugeta Y, Yacob HT, Ashenafi H (2010). Ectoparasites of small ruminants in three selected agro-ecological sites of Tigray Region, Ethiopia. Tropical Animal Health Production 42:1219-1224.

Pangui LJ (1994). Mange in domestic animals and methods of control.

Scientific and Technical Review of the Office International Epiz. 13(4):1227-1243.

Ranjan R, Dua K, Turkar S, Singh H, Singla LD (2014). Successful management of refractory cases of canine demodicosis with homeopathy medicine Graphitis. Journal of Parasitic Diseases 38(4):417-419.

Salih DA, Hussein AM El, Singla LD (2015). Diagnostic approaches for tick-borne haemoparasitic diseases in livestock. Journal of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Health 7(2):45-56.

Sertse T (2004). Investigation on ectoparasites of small ruminants in selected sites of Amhara regional state and their impact on the tanning industry. MSc thesis. Addis Ababa University Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, pp. 40-42

Sertse T, Wossene A (2007a). A study on ectoparasites of sheep and goats in eastern part of Amhara region , Northeast Ethiopia. Small Ruminant Research 69:62-67.

Sertse T, Wossene A (2007b). Effect of ecto-parasite on quality of pickled skins and their impact on the tanning industries in Amhara regional state, Ethiopia. Small Ruminant Research 69(55-61).

Seyoum Z, Tadesse T, Addisu A (2015). Ectoparasites prevalence in small ruminants in and around Sekela, Amhara regional state, Northwest Ethiopia. Journal of Veterinary Medicine, pp. 1-6.

Singh AP, Singla LD, Singh A (2000). A study on the effects of macroclimatic factors on the seasonal population dynamics of *Boophilus micropus* (Canes, 1888) infesting the cross-bred cattle of Ludhiana district. International Journal of Animal Science 15(1):2931.

Solomon A, Workalemahu A, Jabbar MA, Ahmed MM, Hurissa B (2003). Livestock marketing in Ethiopia : A review of structure, performance and development initiatives. Socio-economics and policy research working paper 52. Livestock marketing authority, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

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Steele M, Coste R, Smith JA (1996). *The Tropical Agriculturalist*, Macmillan (London) and CTA (Wageningen), pp. 79-80.

Thrusfield M (2008). *Sampling in veterinary epidemiology*. 2nd ed. London: Blackwell Science.

Tilahun H, Schmidt E (2012). *Spatial Analysis of Livestock Production Patterns in Ethiopia*. Ethiopia Strategy Support Program II (ESSP II) working paper 44, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

UNDP (2018). *Enhancing the productivity of Ethiopia's Livestock Sector*. <https://www.et.undp.org/>. Accessed on 17 Aug 2019.

Urquhart G, Armour J, Duncan J, Dunn A, Jennings F (1996). *Veterinary Parasitology*. 2nded. Oxford: Blackwell Science, pp. 103-113.